

Studies in Sulphonamides: Part II. Preparation of N¹-Hetero-Cyclic Substituted Sulphonamides from Alpha-naphthylamine and Evaluation of their Antibacterial Properties

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A series of N¹-heterocyclic substituted naphthalene sulphonamides have been prepared in which the hydrogen atom of the sulphonamido group has been substituted by different nuclei, viz., thiazole, benzothiazole, pyridine and carbazole rings. All the seventeen compounds so prepared were screened for their antibacterial properties and some of these were found to be active 'in vitro' against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

A number of 2-amino 6-alkoxy benzothiazoles have been prepared and tested for their antimalarial activity. Kyosuke Tsuda and Shigeru Fukushima¹ synthesised 2-sulphanilamido benzothiazole and its several other derivatives which were tested for their antimalarial properties. Kichitaro Takatori and Hiyoshi Nishido² have also reported the preparation of some benzene sulphonamides containing a benzothiazole nucleus.

A. Ya Savitski and E. I. Radionovskaya³ have prepared 3-sulphanilamido carbazole by condensing *p*-acetamidobenzene sulphonyl chloride with 3-aminocarbazole in acetone solution and subsequent deacetylation. The latter process was a difficult one but the free base could be obtained by refluxing the acetamido product with hydrobromic acid and subsequent neutralisation. Armando Novelli⁴ also reported the synthesis of this compound by a slightly different procedure and used aqueous sodium hydroxide (6%) instead of hydrobromic acid for deacetylation.

We have already reported⁵ the preparation and results of biological tests of some naphthalene analogues of sulphanilamide. In continuation of this work coupled with the observations of the earlier workers (*loc. cit.*) and in search of compounds which might exhibit antibacterial or antimalarial activities, it was thought of interest to introduce heterocyclic systems like pyridine, benzothiazole, aminothiazole and carbazole at the N¹-atom of 4-amino-1-naphthalene sulphonamide. The work presented in this communication describes the condensation of 4-acetamido-1-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride with 5-aminopyridine, 2-amino-6-methyl, 6-methoxy and 6-chlorobenzothiazoles, 1-amino and 3-aminocarbazoles. All these amino compounds were prepared by the usual methods and the last two were synthesised according to the method of T.C. Whitner Jr.⁶ Further ten differently substituted 2-aminothiazoles, prepared from simple and *p*-substituted acetophenones and thiourea following the procedure of Dodson and King,⁷ were condensed with 4-acetamido-1-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride.

1. Kyosuke Tsuda and Shigeru Fukushima, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1942, **62**, 64-6.
2. Kichitaro Takatori and Hiyoshi Nishido, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1950, **70**, 271-7.
3. A. Ya. Savitski and E. I. Radionovskaya, *J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1947, **17**, 1451-2.
4. Armando Novelli, *Anal. Soc. Quim. Argentina*, 1940, **28**, 27-90.
5. R. D. Desai, G. S., Saharia and H. S. Sodhi, (*in press*).
6. T. C. Whitner Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2326.
7. R. M. Dodson and L. C. King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242.

All the above reactions were carried out in dry acetone as solvent with dry pyridine as a condensing agent; the reaction mixtures were either heated at 45-50° or kept overnight at room temperature and the acetamido products so obtained are given in Table-I. These were subsequently hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (15-20%) to give the respective 4-amino products entered in Table-II.

These compounds were later screened for their antibacterial activities *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and it was observed that N¹-2' (4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamido) thiazole was most active of all the other thiazole derivatives against both the test organisms. N¹-1'-(4-amino-1-naphthalene sulphonamido) carbazole and N¹-3'-(4-amino-1-naphthalene sulphonamido) carbazole were not active against *E. coli* though the latter compound showed slight activity against *S. aureus*.

The procedure adopted for the preparation of all the products given in Tables I and II is exemplified by two representative preparations described in the experimental part of this paper.

TABLE I

*N*¹-Heterocyclic substituted naphthalene sulphonamides

Com- pound No.	R'	Condensing agent	Reaction temp. °C	Time for the reaction (hrs.)	Solvent	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	2-Thiazolyl	Dry pyridine	45-50	2	Ethanol	Dark brown crystals	263	49.9
2.	4-Methyl-2- thiazolyl	Pyridine and acetone.	Room Temp.	Overnight	„	Light violet needles	270 (d)	38.8
3.	4-Phenyl-2- thiazolyl	Dry pyridine	„	„	Absolute alcohol	Grey crystals	285 (d)	52.9
4.	4-(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl)- 2-thiazolyl	Dry pyridine and acetone.	35-45	3	Gl. Acetic acid	Dark brown Crystals	280	42.5
5.	4(<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl)- 2-thiazolyl	„	45.50	2	Ethanol	Brown crystals	245	60.8
6.	4(<i>p</i> -Methoxy-phenyl)- 2-thiazolyl	„	Room Temp.	Overnight	Absolute alcohol	Yellowish brown crystals	185-6	53.7
7.	4:5-Dimethyl-2- thiazolyl	Dry pyridine	„	„	Gl. Acetic acid	Light grey crystals	200 (d)	51.5
8.	4-Methyl-5- carboxy-2- thiazolyl	Dry pyridine and acetone	Room Temp.	Overnight	Ethanol	Grey crystals	262	63.1
9.	4-Phenyl-5-iodo- 2-thiazolyl	„	„	„	„	Red crystals	100-1	58.8
10.	4:5-Diiodo-2- thiazolyl	Dry pyridine	„	„	Glacial acetic acid.	Light violet crystals	300(d)	56.4
11.	6-Methyl-benzo- thiazolyl	Dry pyridine and acetone	50	5	„	Light pink crystals	265(d)	50.3

TABLE I (Contd.)

Compound No.	R'	Condensing agent	Reaction temp. °C	Time for the reaction (hrs.)	solvent	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Yield %
12.	6-Methoxy-benzo-thiazolyl	Dry pyridine and acetone	40-5	3	Absolute alcohol	Greyish black crystals	155-6	55.9
13.	6-Chloro-benzo-thiazolyl	„	40-5	3	Glacial acetic acid	Brown crystals	187-8	59.9
14.	2-Pyridyl	Dry pyridine	40-5	2	„	Dark violet crystals	215-6	50.8
15.	5-Iodo-pyridyl	Dry pyridine and acetone.	50	1	„	Greyish black leaflets	300(d)	34.2
16.	1-Carbazolyl	Acetone	50	5	„	Brown crystals	190	27.2
17.	3-Carbazolyl	Dry pyridine and acetone.	50	½	„	Yellowish white leaflets.	212	35

TABLE II

*N*¹-Heterocyclic substituted naphthalene sulphonamides (R=H)

Compound No.	Mol. Formula	Solvent	Crystalline appearance	M.P. °C	Carbon %		Hydrogen %		Sulphur %	
					Found	Requires	Found	Requires	Found	Requires
1.	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	Ethanol	Light grey crystals.	175-6	51.3	51.1	3.8	3.5	20.7	21.0
2.	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	„	Dark violet needles.	300(d)	52.8	52.6	4.3	4.1	19.8	20.1
3.	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	„	Light violet crystals.	265	60.1	59.8	3.7	3.9	16.6	16.8
4.	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	„	Bright yellow needles.	194	53.8	53.5	3.4	3.2	14.9	15.0
5.	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	„	Yellowish brown crystals.	222-3	54.6	54.8	3.7	3.4	15.1	15.4
6.	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂	Absolute alcohol	Light brown crystals.	149-50	58.5	58.3	4.3	4.1	15.3	15.6
7.	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	Ethanol	Pink crystals.	201-2	54.3	54.0	4.8	4.5	18.9	19.2
8.	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	Absolute alcohol	Pink prisms	165	52.4	52.1	4.5	4.3	16.1	16.4
9.	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ I	Absolute alcohol	Yellowish brown crystals.	134-5	44.7	44.9	2.9	2.7	12.4	12.5
10.	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ I ₂	Ethanol	Dark brown crystals	300(d)	28.4	28.0	1.9	1.6	11.2	11.5
11.	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	„	Brown needles.	300(d)	58.8	58.5	4.3	4.0	17.1	17.3
12.	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂	Absolute alcohol	Light brown needles	179-80	56.3	56.1	4.0	3.9	16.3	16.6
13.	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	Ethanol	Light pinkish crystals	280(d)	52.5	52.3	3.4	3.1	16.0	16.4
14.	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	Acetone	Brown Powder	250(d)	60.4	60.2	4.6	4.3	10.5	10.7
15.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ SI	Absolute alcohol	Dark brown powder	300(d)	42.3	42.1	2.9	2.6	7.3	7.5
16.	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	Ethanol	Dark brown crystals	250-2	68.0	68.2	4.5	4.3	8.4	8.3
17.	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	Absolute alcohol	Yellow leaflets,	232	68.5	68.2	4.6	4.3	8.5	8.3

EXPERIMENTAL

*N*¹-2' (4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamido) thiazole : To a solution of 2-aminothiazole (3.0 g; 0.03 mol) in acetone (45 ml) contained in a R. B. flask (150 ml) was added 4-acetamido 1-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride (8.5 g; 0.03 mol) in small portions followed by the addition of dry pyridine (4.9 ml; 0.06 mol) with constant shaking. The contents were refluxed at 45-50° for 2 hr. and poured into ice cold water (50 ml) containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml.). The brown coloured solid which separated out, was filtered at the suction, washed with water and dried. Pure *N*¹-2' (acetamido -1-naphthalene sulphonamido) thiazole was crystallised from ethanol, in dark brown crystals, m.p. 263° (decomp). (Yield : 5.2 g; 49.9%).

The above acetamido product (3 g) was refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (30 ml; 15%) for 30 mins; the cooled alkaline solution was diluted with water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid until precipitation was complete. The deposited solid was filtered at the suction, washed with water and dried; pure *N*¹-2' (4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamido) thiazole was crystallised from ethanol as a light grey crystalline mass, m.p. 175-6°. (Yield : 2.1 g; 79.6%).

*N*¹-3' (4-Amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamido) carbazole: 4-Acetamido 1-naphthalene sulphonyl chloride (8.5 g; 0.03 mol) was gradually added to a mixture of 3-aminocarbazole (5.5 g; 0.03 mol), dry acetone (40 ml) and dry pyridine (8.5 g; 0.03 mol) contained in a R.B. flask (150 ml) and the contents refluxed at 50° for 30 minutes. The reaction mixture on cooling was diluted with water, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (50 ml) and the precipitated product filtered at the suction, washed with water and dried. Pure *N*¹-3' (4-acetamido 1-naphthalene sulphonamido) carbazole on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid in yellowish white leaflets, had m.p. 212°. (Yield : 4.5 g; 35%).

The above acetylated product (2.5 g) was refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (40 ml; 15%), the hot solution filtered, neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid until the reaction mixture was faintly alkaline to litmus. The deposited solid was filtered at the suction, washed and dried; it melted at 229-30°. Pure *N*¹-3' (4-amino 1-naphthalene sulphonamido) carbazole was crystallised from absolute alcohol in yellow leaflets, m.p. 231-2°. (Yield : 1.5 ; 66.4%).

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